

Digital entrepreneur: The power of digital influence on the consumption of goods and services

Empreendedor Digital: O poder da influência digital no consumo de bens e serviços

Empreendedor digital: El poder de la influencia digital en el consumo de bienes y servicios

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Abstract: Digital entrepreneurship, driven by social networks, has become fundamental to the growth of companies in a competitive market. This study analyzes the impact of digital influencers in generating new consumption, focusing on how their recommendations influence consumers' purchasing decisions. The objectives include identifying the factors that motivate consumers to purchase products through these influencers and proposing strategies to optimize this relationship. The research was carried out through a literature review and analysis of market data. The results suggest that digital influencers have a substantial impact on purchasing behavior, particularly among young individuals. The study also highlights the opportunities and challenges of digital entrepreneurship, including the need for constant adaptation and risk management associated with maintaining a strong brand image. Thus, the strategic use of influencers can increase a company's visibility and stimulate new consumption, making this practice a powerful tool for digital marketing.

Keywords: *Digital entrepreneurship; Digital influencers; Influencer marketing.*

Resumo: O empreendedorismo digital, impulsionado pelas redes sociais, tornou-se fundamental para o crescimento de empresas em um mercado competitivo. Este estudo analisa o impacto dos influenciadores digitais na geração de novos consumos, focando em como suas recomendações influenciam as decisões de compra dos consumidores. Os objetivos incluem identificar os fatores que motivam os consumidores a adquirir produtos através desses influenciadores e propor estratégias para otimizar essa relação. A pesquisa foi realizada por meio de uma revisão bibliográfica e análise de dados de mercado. Os resultados mostram que influenciadores digitais têm um papel significativo no comportamento de compra,

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especialmente entre o público jovem. O estudo também destaca oportunidades e desafios do empreendedorismo digital, como a necessidade de adaptação constante e a gestão de riscos associados à imagem das marcas. Assim, o uso estratégico de influenciadores pode aumentar a visibilidade das empresas e estimular novos consumos, tornando essa prática uma ferramenta poderosa para o marketing digital.

Palavras-chave: Empreendedorismo digital; Influenciadores digitais; Marketing de influência.

Resumen: El emprendimiento digital, impulsado por las redes sociales, se ha convertido en fundamental para el crecimiento de las empresas en un mercado competitivo. Este estudio analiza el impacto de los influencers digitales en la generación de nuevos consumos, enfocándose en cómo sus recomendaciones influyen en las decisiones de compra de los consumidores. Los objetivos incluyen identificar los factores que motivan a los consumidores a adquirir productos a través de estos influenciadores y proponer estrategias para optimizar esta relación. La investigación se realizó a través de una revisión bibliográfica y análisis de datos de mercado. Los resultados muestran que los influencers digitales tienen un papel significativo en el comportamiento de compra, especialmente entre el público joven. El estudio también destaca las oportunidades y los desafíos del emprendimiento digital, como la necesidad de una adaptación constante y la gestión de riesgos asociados con la imagen de marca. Así, el uso estratégico de influencers puede aumentar la visibilidad de las empresas y estimular nuevos consumos, haciendo de esta práctica una poderosa herramienta para el marketing digital.

Palabras clave: *Emprendimiento digital; Influenciadores digitales; Marketing de influenciadores.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Digital entrepreneurship refers to the creation and management of businesses in the online sphere. It is a marketing approach that leverages digital transformation and the opportunities offered by the Internet and digital technologies (SEBRAE, 2023).

The rise of digital entrepreneurship has profoundly transformed the way consumers interact with brands and products. At the heart of this transformation is the digital influencer, a figure whose ability to impact purchasing decisions and shape new consumer trends has been widely recognized. This influence manifests itself in various ways across society, reflecting the impact of their recommendations on consumer behavior in the purchase of products or services.

This study, entitled "Digital Entrepreneurship: The Power of Digital Influence on the Consumption of Goods and Services," aims to explore the crucial role that these influencers play in today's market dynamics and understand how their impact can be maximized for the benefit of businesses.

The central research problem is to investigate whether digital influencers effectively contribute to the increase in new consumption and, if so, what mechanisms are behind this phenomenon. The relevance of this research lies in its potential to offer valuable insights into how companies can adapt their strategies to capitalize on digital influence and attract new customers. In a scenario where the market is increasingly competitive, and consumer expectations are constantly evolving, understanding these factors can provide a significant advantage for entrepreneurs and managers.

The primary objective of this research is to identify the motivating factors that lead to the acquisition of products and services through digital influencers to increase the visibility of companies. To achieve this objective, the following specific objectives will be addressed: i) Examine the role of digital influencers in market dynamics; ii) Identify the motivational factors that contribute to the increase in new consumption; and iii) Propose strategies that take advantage of digital influence to generate new consumption.

The methodology adopted for this research involves a detailed literature review of the existing literature on the topic, including academic journals, relevant articles and electronic sources. This approach will enable an in-depth understanding of the impacts of digital influence and provide a solid basis for formulating practical strategies for the business sector.

Several recent studies support the growing role of digital influencers. According to Freberg, Graham, McGaughey and Freberg LA (2011), digital influencers have the power to significantly shape consumer opinions and behaviors, influencing purchasing decisions and brand perception. Additionally, a study conducted by Kim and Ko (2012) showed that influencers' credibility and engagement are key factors influencing the effectiveness of digital marketing campaigns. These insights underscore the importance of understanding how digital influencers can be leveraged to drive new consumption and benefit companies.

2. THEORETICAL BASIS

A theoretical review was conducted to substantiate the subject and central aspects of Digital Entrepreneurship, reflecting the analysis of digital influencers and drawing parallels on the advantages and opportunities of being an entrepreneur in the digital world through market analysis that becomes dynamic, generating new consumers.

2.1 Entrepreneurship

According to Dornelas: "The entrepreneur is the one who destroys the existing economic order by introducing new products and services, by creating new forms of organization or by exploring new resources and materials" (DORNELAS, 2017, our translation). In other words, the entrepreneur is the one who drives the market to adapt to changes in consumption by encouraging forms of consumption that best meet people's needs in favor of consumer behavior that is constantly evolving, whether due to social or environmental changes.

Using innovation to their advantage, entrepreneurs are always looking to see things in different ways, giving them new meanings and values. Whether seeking to improve processes or stand out competitively in the market, change is always connected to those who "react to it and explore it as an opportunity" (Drucker, p. 36, 2016).

2.2 Digital entrepreneurship

This type of entrepreneur is "one who has a business whose processes and relationships with partners, customers and employees are carried out mainly digitally" (SEBRAE, 2018, p. 9, our translation). Wherever they can work on a plan that is advantageous for their growth and development, they stand out for their intense use of digital tools, which leads to the development of innovative and flexible business models capable of reaching global markets with reduced costs and high scalability.

The virtual entrepreneur must be an individual who possesses all the requirements to be an entrepreneur, with some additional evident qualities, such as innovation management and trend identification. (Gomes, 2003, p. 15).

Dornelas (2016) defines a digital entrepreneur as someone who uses the online environment to develop businesses that do not require a physical presence, allowing rapid adaptation to market and technological changes.

In Brazil, digital entrepreneurship is booming, with forecasts of continued growth in the e-commerce sector. It is estimated that the country could lead the development of this market until 2027, with an average annual growth rate of 14.6%. Additionally, many digital entrepreneurs utilize these initiatives as a supplementary source of income, enabling experimentation and market expansion (SEBRAE, 2023).

Based on an analysis of the data presented, it is understood that the digital

entrepreneur not only revolutionizes the market with technological innovations but also rethinks consumer relations and traditional business processes. He is an essential agent in the modern economy, capable of generating value and creating opportunities in a constantly evolving environment.

2.3 Digital influencer

A Digital Influencer is someone who can influence the behavior and opinions of thousands of people through content published on their communication channels, such as Instagram, Facebook and YouTube (Nogueira, 2019). This is a relatively new profession in the market. They work with content production and, as the name suggests, utilize their influence on a segmented niche of people who share their opinions and seek references for their attitudes and purchasing decisions (ALSO, 2018).

This influencer has become a valuable partner for companies and brands on social media, thanks to their large number of followers and the potential digital visibility that significantly expands the reach of their posted content.

Furthermore, to reach a large audience, they need to dedicate time to interacting with their followers and developing ideas for new content, keeping their audience engaged with their posts. This way, they can segment their target audience (QUINTANILHA, 2019).

2.4 Opportunities and advantages of undertaking in the digital universe

With numerous opportunities and advantages, digital entrepreneurship has established itself as a significant alternative for those seeking to start their own business.

New business models with lower costs and greater market reach have been made possible by technological advances and the expansion of the Internet. According to a report by the National Telecommunications Agency (ANATEL), the number of internet users in Brazil exceeds 152 million, which highlights the potential of the digital market for entrepreneurs (ANATEL, 2023). For those looking to enter the business world, this environment offers opportunities without requiring a substantial initial investment.

One of the main advantages of working in the digital world is the flexibility of operations. Entrepreneurs can manage their businesses from anywhere and at any time, which increases efficiency and reduces dependence on physical structures. This paradigm is evident in the case of Magazine Luiza, which transformed its operations into a digital platform that connects suppliers and consumers in a virtual environment. This strategy not only increased reach but also reduced operating costs and increased the range of products offered (MAGALU, 2021).

Furthermore, the digital world allows for more precise audience segmentation. Data analysis and digital marketing tools enable entrepreneurs to gain a deeper understanding of their customers and refine their strategies more effectively.

Nubank, for example, has become one of the leading fintech companies in Latin America through its personalized customer service and effective digital marketing strategies. One of the primary advantages of digital entrepreneurship is the ability to understand customer needs and quickly adapt to market changes (NUBANK, 2022).

Democratization of market access is another positive aspect. Entrepreneurs from various regions of Brazil can compete with large companies by utilizing digital platforms and social networks. The integrated e-commerce platform enables small businesses to establish their online stores at reduced costs, facilitating access to e-commerce and increasing competition (LOJA INTEGRADA, 2022). This demonstrates that the digital environment is inclusive, allowing the growth of new businesses regardless of their geographic location.

Another benefit of digital entrepreneurship is that it can help businesses grow. Small companies have the option of scaling up their operations quickly without the need for significant structural changes. This is the case, for instance, of iFood, which began as a startup and has since become one of the leading companies in Latin America through the effective use of digital platforms and delivery technology (iFood, 2023). Therefore, the digital world offers not only countless business opportunities but also competitive advantages that can be crucial to a company's success.

2.5 Market dynamics

Technology has been increasingly present in people's lives, a means by which digital influencers use it to communicate with their “followers” and influence them to consume goods and services.

According to SEBRAE (2023), “72.5 million households had access to the Internet (92.5%) in Brazil. In urban areas, the percentage increased from 93.5% to 94.1% and in rural areas, from 78.1% to 81.0%” (our translation). Data from the Continuous National Household Sample Survey – PNAD on the Information and Communication Technology – ICT module, carried out in 2023 by IBGE.

In other words, more than 90% of the Brazilian population has access to the Internet. This figure tends to increase steadily, as it is now necessary to use the Internet for basic tasks, such as making payments. Due to the advent of Brazilian instant payment (PIX), this method has become the most widely used in 2022 (FEBRABAN, 2022).

Therefore, it is observed that it is possible to reach a large audience through the Internet, as this vast audience now has access to the primary resource used to attract and influence people digitally.

Figure 1 - Households where the Internet was used, by household situation (%)

Source: IBGE (2022-2023)

According to Carpaccio (2021), "the influencer is responsible for 40% of purchases made online (our translation)." The author notes that Brazil has surpassed China and is now the country with the most significant number of consumers influenced by digital marketing, with a growing trend in this new form of encouraging consumption.

A recent study conducted by YouGov (2022) indicates that the influencer marketing sector has doubled in size since 2019, with an expected annual growth rate of 30.3% until 2028. Platforms focused on this marketing medium have already raised more than US\$800 million in funding in 2021, with Instagram representing 80% of brands as a social channel for these digital communications, making the power of influence an undeniable general marketing strategy.

Figure 2 - Probability of consumers being influenced by digital influencers
Consumers are most likely to notice influencer endorsements when purchasing clothes

For each of the following, how likely are you to take notice an endorsement by social media influencers when it comes to purchasing the following products and services? (% of global adults who selected 'a lot' or 'a little')

Source: YouGov (2022)

Figure 2 shows their percentage representation by sector. This research, conducted in 2022 with a sample size ranging from 513 to 2,015 people aged 18 or older across 18 markets, also reveals that among services and/or products most impacted by digital influencers, clothing holds the most significant representation at 46%, followed by food at 45% and entertainment at 44%.

2.6 Generation of new consumption and the impacts of influencer marketing

The growing digitalization and transformation of consumer expectations have significantly influenced the generation of new consumption patterns in Brazil. The advent of digital technologies and increased Internet access has enabled the personalization and diversification of product and service offerings, creating opportunities for companies and entrepreneurs. According to a study by the Brazilian Institute of Geography and Statistics (IBGE), digitalization has driven significant changes in the purchasing behavior of Brazilians, who increasingly seek convenience and innovation (IBGE, 2023).

The concept of a collaborative economy has played a crucial role in driving new consumption patterns. Sharing platforms and services based on the circular economy have encouraged more sustainable consumption and the creation of new business models. Sebrae highlights that Brazilian startups are standing out in their adaptation of these models, taking advantage of the new demand for solutions that prioritize resource conservation and minimize waste (SEBRAE, 2023).

The influence of social media cannot be underestimated either. With the exponential growth in the use of platforms like Instagram and TikTok, consumers are increasingly exposed to trends and innovations that shape their consumption habits. According to research by ComScore, the impact of social media on purchasing decisions is growing, with consumers seeking recommendations and inspiration directly from digital influencers and brands (COMSCORE, 2023).

The growing demand for personalized and interactive experiences reflects a shift in the profile of Brazilian consumers, who prioritize the experience over the mere act of consumption. Studies by Nielsen show that consumers are increasingly interested in experiences that provide deeper engagement and an emotional connection with brands (Nielsen, 2023), highlighting the need for companies to adapt their strategies to meet these new expectations and stand out in a constantly evolving market.

Data from Sebrae (2023) from a study on consumer behavior post-COVID 2022, carried out by the Marco communications agency with a sample of 14,000 people from 14 different countries interviewed to analyze their preferences and behavior, indicates that Brazilians are the most influenced by digital advertising, with 72% of those interviewed considering recommendations from digital influencers and 73% stating that they have already purchased a product or service through this recommendation. The study also adds that among the age groups most impacted are those between 18 and 25 years old,

2.7 Digital influencer as a brand spokesperson: success stories

According to Almeida (2023), Virgínia Fonseca's interview has established itself as a true internet phenomenon, successfully transforming its enormous popularity into a business success. A clear example is WePink, her cosmetics brand, which has had an impressive performance since its inception. In its first month of operation, in October 2021, the company earned more than R\$10 million. In 2023, Virgínia achieved another significant milestone, raising R\$15 million in just 12 hours during a live broadcast.

This growing success reflects not only Virgínia's ability to attract and engage a massive audience but also her entrepreneurial vision, which positions her as a reference in the digital and business world. In addition to WePink, which started with just five employees, including the three partners, and currently has a team of 119 people, Virgínia Fonseca is also the founder of the influencer agency Talismã Digital and the brand Maria's Baby, which specializes in children's products.

Despite her success in entrepreneurship, Virginia has decided not to open new companies for the time being, preferring to focus her efforts on the brands she already owns.

This approach showcases your strategic vision for sustainable business growth while balancing business management with your personal life and active social media presence.

In recent years, several influencers, particularly from the fashion and beauty sectors, have leveraged the engagement generated on social media to develop their businesses, following the beauty standards imposed by society that disproportionately affect young people from Generation Z, who are in direct and constant contact with the digital world.

According to Silva (2023), the study is essential to understanding the influence that these brands exert, considering that the selected profiles have strong persuasive power in the virtual community in which they operate. Based on this approach, an analysis was conducted of specific profiles that reflect the current patterns of engagement and performance in the digital market.

One of the profiles discussed was that of Bianca Andrade da Silva, popularly known as Boca Rosa. It is worth noting that the profile reflects her vibrant and engaged personality. With over 18 million followers, Bianca is one of the prominent Instagram personalities in Brazil and other Portuguese-speaking countries.

The content published primarily focuses on beauty, fashion, lifestyle, and her personal life. Influencer Marketing, as we know it today, gained a decisive impact with the emergence of social networks and, consequently, absorbed an increasingly larger share of investment in communication, becoming essential for various industries, particularly in Fashion, Beauty, and Lifestyle brands (BAILES, 2018). Regarding formats, she primarily shares photos and videos of her looks, as well as makeup and skincare tips, along with updates on her projects and personal life. Her brand contributes to the formation of aesthetic standards and

the dissemination of beauty ideals, which directly impact the perception of millions of followers on social networks. In this way, Bianca engages in social causes, such as the fight against domestic violence and the promotion of education, building a relationship with her followers.

In an article by Storch (2021), Tiago Nigro stands out as an example of a digital influencer who covers various niches, with each segment catering to the specific needs of his audience. Nigro stands out in the field of financial education, providing highly relevant content for his followers. With a degree in International Relations from ESPM, he has several certifications that qualify him to work in the capital markets. He offers a series of courses focused on achieving financial independence, impacting millions of people through his profile, "O Primo Rico."

The combination of essential topics and the consistency of his publications enabled him to achieve broad visibility, solidifying his reputation as a reference in this sector. Platforms that address significant issues tend to increase the impact and reach of influencers like Nigro.

On YouTube, his channel boasts over 6.6 million subscribers, while on Instagram, he has garnered more than 8 million followers. Therefore, Nigro reaches 448.5 thousand followers on X (formerly Twitter) and 669 thousand on Facebook. The interview reveals that the number of influencers who shared content about the investment sector reached 515 in the latest survey, remaining stable compared to the previous edition. On the other hand, the total number of monitored profiles showed a slight 1% reduction in the same period.

Storch highlights that Tiago Nigro, known as "O primo rico," transformed his life story upon entering the digital market. Since then, he has released books that reflect his experiences and vision of finance, consolidating his influence in the area. After facing rejections from publishers, his first book, "Do Mil ao Milhão Sem Cortar o Cafézinho," released in 2018, became one of the best-selling books in Brazil. Today, he has millions of followers and is a reference in the financial sector.

2.8 Negative impacts of digital influence

Digital influencers have become a prominent presence on social media, shaping behaviors and promoting consumer trends. Even though this influence also has considerable negative impacts, especially concerning the mental health of followers. Many influencers display an idealized and unattainable lifestyle, promoting standards of beauty and success that can generate anxiety, depression and low self-esteem, particularly among young people, who are more susceptible to social comparisons. The pressure to meet these unrealistic standards is a constant on social media, where the "perfect" life shown in posts is far from reality.

The actions of influencers contribute to rampant consumerism. The incessant promotion of products and lifestyles through social media encourages followers to associate happiness and success with the possession of material goods. This behavior leads to financial frustration and a sense of inadequacy for those who

struggle to keep pace with consumer trends (PORTAL INSIGHTS, 2024). Influence goes beyond the simple purchase of products and reaches the way of life, creating a consumer culture that devalues deeper aspects of personal satisfaction.

In recent years, issues related to the civil liability of influencers have emerged. Promoting products without due transparency regarding commercial agreements has become a common problem. Many influencers do not make it clear that their recommendations are paid, misleading their followers and undermining the trust established. Furthermore, in extreme cases, influencers have been held liable for promoting harmful or even illegal products, as in the case of gambling platforms that financially harm their followers (CÉSAR, 2023; VEJA, 2024). These events highlight the need for stricter regulation of the role of these professionals in digital advertising.

The relentless pursuit of engagement on social media has contributed to the deterioration of authenticity. Many influencers resort to artificial strategies to gain more followers and likes without considering the social impact of their actions. This race for popularity creates a toxic environment where the value of a person or content is measured by the number of likes rather than the quality or veracity of the information (EXAME, 2023). Cancel culture, associated with this search for social acceptance, also contributes to a digital environment of intolerance, harming the mental health of influencers and followers.

Although the digital market offers a variety of opportunities, demonstrating that it is possible to achieve both financial returns and personal satisfaction through this career, some disadvantages are often overlooked when an influencer becomes a public figure. Cancellation is a common practice in the digital environment, which occurs when a public figure, such as an actor, singer, or influencer, adopts an attitude or position that displeases their audience. This situation can negatively impact the professional's image and credibility. Furthermore, the influencer must contend with a relentless work routine and the financial uncertainty that characterizes this career (JUNIOR, HERZER, FERREIRA, 2023).

It is essential to highlight the social exclusion faced by those who do not fit into established standards, becoming victims of bullying by groups already consolidated in society, which further aggravates their emotional state. These aggressions are not restricted to the physical environment, as they also manifest themselves in the digital world, where cases of cyberbullying occur. Finally, the pressure to maintain a constant online presence can lead to mental exhaustion (Silva, 2023). Although digital influencers have a considerable audience, negative signs of this phenomenon are beginning to emerge on the Internet (VEJA, 2024).

In this way, digital influencers, previously seen as mere product promoters, are now revealed to be key players in criminal schemes. The promotion of illegal gambling, such as "Jogo do Tigrinho" on the Blaze platform, highlights the persuasive power of these personalities and the need for greater oversight of their activities (VEJA, 2024). Low-income young people are the most affected by online gambling, which initially appears as a form of entertainment but ends up

compromising a significant part of their budget on gambling, reflecting financial difficulties with common consumer goods.

Highly renowned influencers in Brazil, such as Carlinhos Maia and Rico Melquiades, have typically stated that they would not be held responsible for followers who take risks in casinos, claiming that it is an individual choice. "If I say: 'Jump off the cliff', said Carlinhos Maia to his 29 million followers". (VEJA, 2024). This lack of responsibility emphasizes the need for greater awareness of the consequences of one's actions and the importance of sound ethics when promoting products and lifestyles.

3. METHOD

This study employed a descriptive exploratory research design, aiming to find answers to the proposed questions. The research methods employed in this study were informed by existing studies, drawing on books and academic search databases. Thus, content analysis is considered a 'set of research analysis techniques' aimed at obtaining, through systematic and objective procedures of describing the content of messages, indicators (quantitative or not) that allow the inference of knowledge related to the prediction/reception conditions (inferred variables) of these messages (BARDIN, 2011).

The study was designed to investigate the influence of digital influencers on the acquisition of products and services. The research was developed through the following steps:

Literature Review: A comprehensive analysis of the current literature on digital influencers was conducted, encompassing academic journals, relevant articles, and electronic sources. This stage sought to consolidate knowledge about the impact of influencers on purchasing decisions and brand perception.

Analysis of Recent Studies: A review of recent studies examining influencer credibility and engagement was conducted. Research from SEBRAE and electronic magazines provided relevant information.

Identification of Motivational Factors: Based on the literature review, the main motivational factors that lead consumers to purchase products and services through digital influencers were identified.

Strategies: Based on the insights obtained, practical recommendations were presented to enable companies to effectively leverage digital influence, thereby increasing their visibility and attracting new consumers.

This methodology provided a solid basis for understanding the mechanisms that connect digital influencers to increased consumption, contributing to the development of more effective business strategies. Above all, a deficiency was observed when seeking financial information about the impact of influencers on product sales and their representativeness.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This research aimed to investigate the impact of digital entrepreneurship, specifically the role of digital influencers in driving new consumption. The data obtained throughout the research confirms the growing relevance of these influencers in consumer behavior, revealing a dynamic changing market.

4.1 Digital Influence on the Consumption of Goods and Services

Digital influencers have emerged as central figures in companies' marketing strategies due to their ability to influence purchasing behaviors. According to data from YouGov (2022), influencer marketing has doubled in size since 2019 and is expected to grow at a rate of 303% per year until 2028, with platforms such as Instagram leading this market, accounting for around 80% of campaigns. These numbers corroborate the relevance of this type of strategy for brands seeking to reach new audiences in a segmented way.

The research reinforces that, according to Capomaccio (2021), 40% of purchases made in Brazil are directly influenced by recommendations from digital influencers. Brazil stands out as the country with the most significant number of consumers influenced by digital marketing, surpassing countries such as China. This reality highlights the pivotal role of digital influencers in marketing strategies, serving as a crucial tool for driving new consumption.

4.2 Generation of New Consumption

The analysis of the results indicates that digital influence has a significant impact on generating new consumption. Studies by IBGE (2023) show that digitalization and increased internet access have enabled the diversification and personalization of product and service offerings. Companies that employ these strategies can create consumption habits, promoting not only products but also personalized experiences. This digital transformation is also linked to the demand for innovation, which generates new consumption opportunities in sectors such as fashion, food, and entertainment.

The Nielsen (2023) study also highlighted the growing demand for interactive experiences, reflecting a shift in the profile of the modern consumer. Instead of being content with simply purchasing a product, consumers are seeking a deeper and more meaningful experience with brands, which can only be achieved through effective communication on digital platforms.

4.3 Impact on Consumer Behaviors

The results indicate that influencer marketing has the potential to influence consumer behavior and drive market trends. According to SEBRAE (2023), 73% of Brazilians have already made a purchase influenced by recommendations from digital influencers. The primary age groups most susceptible to these recommendations are young people aged 18 to 25, with 57% representation,

with the fashion sector standing out as the most significantly impacted.

This shift in consumer behavior is driven by increased digital connectivity and trust in influencer recommendations. As a result, brands have increasingly turned to influencers as spokespeople, especially when the influencer's audience aligns with the brand's target demographic.

4.4 Opportunities for Digital Entrepreneurship

Digital entrepreneurship presents a diverse range of opportunities for companies seeking to expand their market presence. With the Internet, entrepreneurs can reach global markets with reduced costs and high scalability, as reported by SEBRAE (2018). Innovative business models, such as e-commerce and collaborative platforms, have facilitated the emergence of new digital ventures.

Nevertheless, the challenges are also considerable. Competitiveness in the digital environment requires entrepreneurs to be constantly aware of changes in consumer trends and technological innovation. The use of digital influencers, although advantageous, can generate risks related to brand image and liability for the products promoted, as highlighted by César (2023), who addresses ethical issues and compliance with advertising regulations.

4.5 Challenges of Digital Entrepreneurship

One of the challenges in the digital environment is cancellation, which can harm the image of both influencers and the brands associated with them. Cancellation occurs when influencers or companies are publicly criticized for inappropriate behavior or statements, resulting in the loss of contracts and damage to their reputation. Exame (2020) reports the case of Gabriela Pugliesi, who, during the pandemic, hosted a party, generating negative repercussions and leading brands such as Rappi to cancel contracts. This example highlights how the image of influencers can be volatile, directly affecting the companies with which they have commercial ties.

Another relevant case was that of Carlinhos Maia, who was criticized for making controversial comments during the pandemic, resulting in a loss of trust among his followers and negatively affecting the brands that sponsored him (VEJA, 2024). These cases underscore the importance of companies carefully selecting influencers and aligning with their values. According to César (2023), transparency and accountability are essential for maintaining consumer trust in influencer marketing campaigns, thereby reducing the risks that cancellation can pose to a brand's reputation.

5. CONCLUSION

A study on the impact of digital entrepreneurship, focusing on digital influencers, revealed how these figures have become key players in marketing strategies, particularly in an increasingly digitalized environment. Influencers' ability to build

authentic and highly engaging connections with their followers positions them as effective intermediaries between brands and consumers, particularly in sectors such as fashion, entertainment and food. These results underscore the importance of influencer marketing strategies in attracting new consumers and enhancing brand recognition, thereby creating significant opportunities for business growth.

However, the research also highlighted the challenges associated with utilizing digital influencers. The risk of cancellation and the effects of a misalignment of values between influencers and brands can harm the image of both. Cases in which influencers have been criticized for inappropriate behavior and lost contracts with large companies serve as a warning of the need for careful selection of spokespersons. Therefore, ethical issues and responsibility for the content promoted were also raised, especially concerning the advertising of harmful or controversial products, such as gambling.

The study also revealed the potentially negative impact of digital influence on consumer behavior, especially among younger consumers. Constantly promoting idealized lifestyles on social media can lead to anxiety, frustration, and excessive consumption. When using this marketing strategy, brands must be careful to strike a balance between encouraging consumption and promoting values that do not contribute to the creation of unattainable standards. This highlights the need for stricter regulation and greater transparency in marketing campaigns that involve influencers.

Although influencer marketing has shown great potential for growth and innovation, the study recognizes that measuring the direct financial impacts of these strategies is a limitation. Future research could focus on a more detailed analysis of economic data, providing a clearer view of the return on investment generated through the use of digital influencers. This will enable a more accurate assessment of the real value that this type of strategy offers to companies across various sectors.

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